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Sloshing Wing Dynamics – Project Overview

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Abstract

The SLOshing Wing Dynamics (SLOWD) project aims to investigate the modelling of fuel sloshing physics to reduce the design loads on aircraft structures. This goal will be achieved through investigating the damping effect of sloshing on the dynamics of flexible wing-like structures carrying liquid (fuel) via the development of experimental set-ups complemented by novel numerical and analytical tools.

The primary focus of the project is the application of modelling capabilities to the wing design of large civil passenger aircraft (subject to EASA CS-25 type certification), which are designed to withstand the loads occurring from atmospheric gusts, turbulence and landing impacts. The timeframe of the project is three years, starting in September 2019.

Keywords: Fluid-Structure Interaction; Aviation; Certification.

1. Introduction

Large passenger aircraft produced in the European Union are designed to meet the regulatory requirements of Certification Specification 25 (CS25), as defined by the airworthiness authority - the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA).

The wings of such aircraft are highly flexible structures, which can deform significantly when, for example, atmospheric turbulence or a gust is encountered. Typical limit deformations can reach 20% of the wing span. Wings also house the fuel tanks, and generally carry an amount of fuel comparable in weight to that of their structural components. For a typical wing of a single aisle aircraft, with maximum take-off weight of 100 tonnes and 3000nmi range, both structural and fuel weights are of the order of 4 to 6 tonnes.

The standard engineering practices for wing (and aircraft) design do not consider the effect of the fuel movement within the tanks for the determination of the aircraft design loads. This is due to the lack of maturity of the current toolsets available to industry.

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The typical aircraft development cycle includes two major types of tests to identify/verify the dynamic characteristics of the aircraft structure and its characteristic excitations:

- Ground Vibration Test (GVT), performed before first flight. The aircraft is made to vibrate by mechanical means so that its structural behavior (including damping) can be measured. It is standard practice to repeat the test for the two extreme conditions of either empty or full tanks.
- Flutter Flight Test (FFT), usually performed via prescribed oscillatory motion of the aircraft control surfaces (such as ailerons) when flying at speed close to the design envelope of the aircraft. Results from the FFT campaign are generally used to adjust the unsteady external aerodynamic model used to excite the structural model.

Both above tests are limited to small amplitudes and are therefore not likely to excite significant sloshing modes. In the case of the GVT, this is to avoid damaging the specimen (usually the first production aircraft), and the FFT to avoid endangering the safety of crew and aircraft. Also significant is that these qualification tests are performed after the design of the fuel tanks is finalized.

The EASA certification specifications offer the possibility to relax the conservatism inherent to these industrial practices, in fact the CS-25 Acceptable Means of Compliance (AMC) 25.341 6. c. (Gust and Continuous Turbulence Design Criteria) state:

“Structural dynamic models may include damping properties in addition to representations of mass and stiffness distributions. In the absence of better information, it will normally be acceptable to assume 0.03 (i.e. 1.5% equivalent critical viscous damping) for all flexible modes. Structural damping may be increased over the 0.03 value to be consistent with the high structural response levels caused by extreme gust intensity, provided justification is given.”

Therefore SLOWD aims at quantifying, via a holistic approach (both experimental and numerical), the extent to which liquid sloshing in the aircraft tanks affects the “*structural damping*” mentioned in the AMC above, or more in general the structural dynamic behavior of an airliner, at “*high structural response levels*”. In addition, the identification of the architectural parameters to maximize fuel slosh induced damping will overcome the major shortfalls of the current industrial practices: conservatism in the design loads calculation and inability to maximize the benefits related to sloshing-induced dissipative effects (via informed design of the fuel tank layout).

A substantive increase in the damping characteristics of the structure is expected, as recently demonstrated experimentally by the preliminary work performed by Airbus in collaboration with all the SLOWD consortium partners, Gamboli et Al. (2019a), Gamboli et Al. (2019b), Titurus et Al. (2019). The feasibility of modelling such phenomena with numerical and reduce-order techniques is addressed in the works of Calderon-Sanchez et Al (2019) and Mastroddi et Al (2019).

2. Methods

The partners of the SLOWD project formed a consortium, bringing together industrial know-how and academic research. The institutions involved and the geographical composition of the consortium is shown in Fig. 1.

2.1. Experimental Work

The consortium intends to set up an experimental campaign to investigate the response to dynamic loading of the wings of a modern passenger airliner (200 passengers or more) carrying fuel. The results of the campaign would be a database of measurements for benchmarking the numerical and analytical methods developed during the remainder of the project. The measured quantities will include time-varying parameters (e.g. accelerations, displacements, wall pressures) from which the damping effect of the sloshing will be computed for high amplitude excitations, such as those described in CS25.341 for gust and continuous turbulence and CS25.473 for landing. These tests will investigate and understand the basic governing principles of the coupled Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) problem.

This flexible wing structure will be designed to accommodate a partially-filled tank in which the liquid surface is perturbed by the structural motion and interact with the internal walls of its container. The concept of the test setup is shown in Fig. 2. To ensure a high amplitude response, the wing specimen will be deflected close to its maximum structural capability using the quick-release mechanism and loading collar also shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1 Consortium Geographical Composition

After a settling time for the liquid to find its equilibrium position, the wing will be suddenly released, leaving the structure and the liquid in the tank free to oscillate.

This is similar in principle to the prototype test described by Gamboli et Al. (2019a), but comprises a more realistic wing configuration and different additional excitation modes. The additional complexity is considered necessary, as past industrial experience (Fellows at Al. (2011)) indicates that real-scale testing is required when validating complex modelling elements linked with aircraft safety.

Fig. 2 SLOWD Test Concept

The real-scale tests will be performed on an actual wing specimen with a span of the order of ~16m (Airbus A320 family), with and without liquid to assess the effect of sloshing on its dynamic behavior. The aim of this test is the ultimate validation of the coupled numerical models, and appropriate quantities will be measured to characterize both the structural and fluid dynamics (e.g. accelerations, strains/stresses, wall pressures). Due to

the large scale, and consequent cost (the force required to achieve limit deflection for a wing of this size is of the order of 15 metric tons), the range of excitations and parameters investigated will be relatively limited, focusing on the expected biases between real and small scale.

To precede the real-scale (and prior to its execution), a similar testing campaign will take place at small-scale with a wing specimen of the span of the order of 3m (scale 1:5). The small-scale test will be performed to:

- De-risk the real-scale test, as free release tests of highly dynamic events require assessment of the structural integrity of the wing specimen and testing equipment sensors a-priori.
- Provide a benchmark set of results for the validation of the numerical methods developed in the remainder of the project. Note that compared to the prototype test (Gamboli et al. (2019a)), this small-scale test will introduce additional complexity (e.g. fully 3D wing geometry, coupled bending/torsion excitations).
- Allow for the installation of a broad range of sensing and excitation equipment, for the monitoring of both liquid and solid phases. As an example, high speed cameras and specialized lighting will be employed to observe the liquid free surface, which are unlikely to be installed on the real-scale specimen due to limited access to the fuel tanks. Also, due to the reduced scale, it will be feasible to employ external excitation devices to apply external forces (see Fig. 2) for the validation of active control strategies.
- Allow for a large range of parameters to be investigated, thanks to the reduced cost. As an example, the amount of testing liquid required for the real-scale test is estimated at 1.5 metric tons, in contrast to 10kg for the small-scale test. Therefore, different liquids of various densities and viscosities will be tested. Another practical aspect for consideration is testing with a solid mass equivalent to the liquid (for comparison with the current industrial practices). This is impractical at real-scale due to the high volumes required and the limited access to the fuel tanks, but will be part of the small-scale tests.

The overall strategy behind the physical testing for the project is depicted in the diagram in Figure 5, which shows the relative cost and complexity of the different test types in relation to the number of parametric variations.

Fig. 3 Testing Strategy

The results of the experimental tests will be used for the validation and verification of numerical methods available to the partners. The setup will provide a benchmark method to comply with AMC 25.341 and will be discussed with industry Design Certification Specialists to ensure compliance with the CS25 regulation, and its applicability to aircraft certification programs.

2.2. Effective Use of Numerical Methods

Concurrent modelling of the experimental setup will be performed, allowing further development of numerical methods. The aim of the modelling is twofold; preliminary calculations will be undertaken to inform the design

of the experimental campaign. Subsequently, a high-fidelity digital-twin of the experimental set-up will be generated, which will provide a wealth of data from which reduced order models can be built.

Numerical methods for solid and fluid mechanics are available from academic research groups and commercially, however they all require adaptation to the specific problem of interest. This is particularly true in the non-linear regime (when superposition of effects does not apply). The case under consideration is highly non-linear in nature, in fact:

- Under limit load conditions the wing structure would deform geometrically beyond the remit of small deformation theory.
- The behavior of the liquid free surface is typically non-linear, as the free surface would start to “break” as it interacts with the walls and the air entrapped in the tank. Liquid impact is also highly non-linear and will occur during violent gust events.

Therefore, the dynamics of the complete system cannot be studied by looking at the two problems of solid and fluid mechanics in isolation. Cutting-edge numerical methods must be employed to efficiently couple the available technologies for non-linear structural and fluid dynamics.

The consortium aims to:

- **Make effective use of existing state-of-the-art Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD)** software developed by some of its partners, to accurately simulate the liquid sloshing due to fluid/solid interaction as measured in the experimental tests. Specific emphasis will be on improving methods to account for gas compressibility, non-linear tank rotation (due to the interaction with the structure) and accuracy of modelling the energy dissipation effects due to fluid sloshing.
- **Further develop non-linear Finite Element Models (FEM)**, to accurately simulate the structural dynamics of the wing as measured in the experimental tests. It is particularly important that these models are fast and efficient to allow use in routine aerospace design.
- **Develop conservative and robust CFD/FEM coupling methodologies** for the problem under consideration. This aims to enable accurate simulation of the fully-coupled liquid and wing structure dynamics. The ultimate goal is the **creation of a digital twin of the experimental setup** described in section 2.1.

Fig. 4 Example of CFD/FEM coupling for sloshing

These modelling methods will be implemented in a massively-parallel high-performance computing environment (HPC) due to the large computational costs expected from the calculations, so to enable their use in the industrial design process of civil aircraft.

Fig. 4 gives a graphical representation of the CFD/FEM coupling and shows the type of models and information exchanges involved in the numerical coupling. The full order multi-material model will serve two purposes viz. calibration and evaluation of the reduced-order-models (both fluid and structure) to be developed in the project; as well as develop the ability to compute detailed stresses and slosh damping effects for identified “worst case” scenarios to inform design.

2.3. Reduce Order and Analytical Model Evaluation

A variety of reduced-order and analytical models will be evaluated in terms of their computation efficiency and accuracy in predicting sloshing-related dissipative effects. The reduction in the complexity of the numerical models is deemed necessary for subsequent inclusion into an industrial design framework.

In fact the CS25 regulations require performing a large number of loads calculations, for which experimental or full order (CFD/FEM) models are prohibitively expensive. For this purpose, so called reduced-order-models (ROMs), which are derived and calibrated from full order models as well as experimental data, will be employed. Advanced data analytics techniques are available to build these Reduced Order Models (ROMs), utilizing the experimental and numerical data generated in the earlier phases of the project.

A key objective of the consortium is to define a set of advanced analytical techniques for model-order reduction of the complete (coupled) as well as isolated (fluid/structure) sub-systems. The resulting ROMs will finally be assessed in terms of efficiency and accuracy.

The aim is to integrate these reduced-order /analytical models into a multidisciplinary framework for use in the industrial design process. Such a framework will allow the design of active, as well as passive, controls of the coupled system, the performance of which will be subsequently tested at critical design point using the full order models.

Fig. 5 Aircraft Stick Model with Sloshing Masses

Fig. 5 shows an example of model-order-reduction, where the number of degrees of freedom of the structural FEM is reduced via beam (stick) elements and the liquid sloshing is represented by a series of mass-spring systems.

2.4. Industrial Design Framework

An industrialized version of the numerical and reduced-order methods developed will be used to understand the influence of design parameters such as baffle spacing, baffle openings and fill-level to define an optimal architecture of the wing fuel tanks, hence maximizing the dissipation effects due to fuel sloshing.

A design framework is already available to the consortium partners. As this has been developed for space applications with focus on the development of liquid-propellant management systems, its applicability to aeronautics is of significant interest and will be tested, adapted and evaluated in the project.

The goals of the consortium are:

- To test the overall framework capability with a highly coupled, non-linear problem - at first without any active control.

- To design and implement an active control strategy of the overall system via this framework and evaluate its accuracy against the experimental data. The active control will be achieved, for example, via control of the external forces applied by the actuator shown in Fig. 2.
- To evaluate a different levels of full order model fidelity and determine their applicability to the different phases of the aircraft design process.
- To investigate and calibrate highly-efficient (relatively low fidelity) models for rapid use in the conceptual phase of aircraft development and highly-accurate (relatively low efficiency) models for the calibration and detailed design phases.
- To test the capability of the framework in achieving the optimal design for typical use-cases relevant to industrial design.

Fig. 6 Industrial Framework – Controller Design Capability

Fig. 6 shows the capability of the active-control design envisaged for the framework.

3. Results

Airbus, supported by ArianeGroup and the other partners, set up a prototype test rig at their Protospace laboratory in Filton, UK (see Fig. 7) to investigate sloshing related damping in aircraft wings. The rig comprises a water tank mounted on a 2.35m cantilever and an accelerometer fixed at the free end of the beam. The cantilever is forced into a deflected shape by a ratchet and quick-release mechanism. Once the quick-release is activated, the cantilever is free to oscillate and the decay in the oscillation is recorded by accelerometers. This configuration is broadly representative of a wing and its fuel tank undergoing a step-input type of excitation (similar to that due to a gust).

Fig. 7 Prototype Test Rig

Prototype test results are shown in Fig. 8, where the measured vertical accelerations at the free-end of the cantilever are plotted over time. Two cases are compared here, with the tank carrying a weight equal to 7% of the mass of the cantilever for both. In the “liquid mass” case, the tank is filled with water to 50% of its maximum capacity, while in the “solid mass” case the tank carries the same mass of solid material (ballast). Note that for ease of comparison the vertical response depicted in Fig. 3 for each case (solid ballast and liquid) is normalized with respect to its own initial peak acceleration.

It can be seen from a comparison of the acceleration decays over time that the liquid motion in the tank, induced by the free vibration of the beam, damps the oscillations faster than in the solid case. The time to decay to half of the maximum acceleration is considered here as a first order indicator of the damping characteristic of the oscillating system. In the liquid case about four oscillations ($t = 0.452\text{s}$) are needed for the acceleration to decay to half its maximum amplitude, compared at least six oscillations ($t = 0.757\text{s}$) in the solid case, therefore indicating $\sim 50\%$ increase in the damping characteristics of the system. This has a direct bearing on both static and fatigue life of wing structural components as well as passenger ride comfort.

Fig. 8 Accelerometer Measurements

These initial results demonstrated the viability of investigating the effect of liquid sloshing on the vibration of a flexible wing type structure and provide an order of magnitude for the benefit expected from a more sophisticated analysis. This prototype test also illustrates the concept behind the experimental campaign proposed in SLOWD, which targets more complex geometries (similar to those of an actual aircraft wing) and dynamic structural behaviour (coupled bending and torsion).

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